

EVALUATION FOR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF LOW PRESSURE – TUBULAR FORMED SMC USED FOR SEWER PIPE REHABILITATION

Eiji Kitagawa, Machiko Mizoguchi, Asami Nakai, Hiroyuki Hamada

Kyoto Institute of Technology

Matsugasaki Gosyokaido-cho, Sakyo-ward Kyoto-city Kyoto, Japan

SUMMARY : It has been known that there are many sewer pipes suffered from the acid-stress corrosion, these days, caused by hydrogen sulfide which is generated by bacteria existing inside concrete sewer pipes. In consideration of the current traffic situation in Japan, it is difficult to adopt the conventional open-cut method for the pipe rehabilitation, consequently, the No – Dig method has been attracting attention and widely used in Japan. But because of reduction in the internal diameter of the sewer pipes after lining, it is necessary to use the material which has high strength to make thickness thinner. It can be easily formed with various thickness, resulting in minimal costs. SMC (Sheet Molding Compound) is most suitable material for this objective as lining material. However, since a new GFRP is built inside the pipe by such rehabilitation method, the SMC has to be formed in the tubular shape under very low pressure of 0.1 MPa. This method is quite different from the conventional one which requires high pressure and temperature. It is unavoidable to have many void generated inside the very low pressure- formed SMC, of which mechanical properties do not meet that of the molded SMC under high temperature and pressure. This paper presents the successful development of the very low pressure forming-method for SMC, of which mechanical properties are improved. The development has been implemented by studying the high pressure-temperature molding method and mechanical properties of the product produced by such method.

KEYWORDS : low-pressure molding, SMC, pipe rehabilitation, mechanical property, void

INTRODUCTION

The necessity of a sewer pipe has been recognized in Japan after Cholera was in fashion in 1887, and the sewer of Japan including sewage exclusion in 1884 was made in Tokyo prefecture (present Tokyo), a sewer has been maintained completely with development of industry from 1945 after World War II. The share of sewer pipe reached to 62% in the whole country, and the total extension of the sewer pipe exceeded 300,000km in 1999. Pipeline of total extension exceeded 50 years, namely a life-time, amounted to 6,271km in 1999, currently it is predicted that the pipeline would reach 25,000km after 15 years. It is difficult to exchange a pipe beyond the life because of traffic

circumstance, so pipe rehabilitation method which renews a sewer pipe by trench-less method is beginning to spread.

A high-concentrated sulfide generates acid-condition in the sewer pipes, and this sulfuric acid is one of the causes for corrosion of a concrete pipe. Pipe rehabilitation method is applied under such a high-concentration acid environment, and in addition rehabilitation pipe needs to bear external pressure with only rehabilitation pipe, so PVC or FRP has been used. The thickness of rehabilitation pipe must be changed with change in the external force to bears it only with a pipe. Because the thickness must be changed, SMC (Sheet molding compound) is adopted as a material which can fabricate the pipe with various thickness. SMC products such as bus-tub originally molded under the high pressure of 5MPa. But, in a rehabilitation method for sewer pipe which is called CIPP(Cured in place pipe), molding conditions are restricted ; the SMC has to be molded under very low pressure of 0.1 MPa. It is unsolved problem whether the mechanical properties can achieve a value equivalent to a high-pressure one.

In this paper, the purpose is the establishment of the construction method with improvement in mechanical properties of SMC in low-pressure conditions. A viscosity was measured at different temperature to examine the flow behavior of resin. Next the exothermic curve was measured to know curing condition. Finally the bending test was conducted and the mechanical properties with low pressure was compared to those with high pressure.

BACKGROUD-PROBLEM OF LOW PRESSURE MOLDING

SMC is normally molded with high-pressure and high temperature, for example temperature of 140 °C and pressure of 5MPa, and recently a method of relatively low-pressure molding is established, for example pressure is 2MPa. But because pipe rehabilitation method is molded using sewer pipe as a flame, if the inner pressure about 2MPa is applied to sewer pipe, sewer pipe is damaged. Therefore, inner pressure for molding into sewer pipe must be held down in less than 0.1MPa. This is able to be called super low-pressure molding. In addition, heating is applied under the special condition which is limited to single-sided heating from inside of a sewer pipe. In case of super low-pressure molding like 0.1MPa, it is considered that void remained after curing. If void remained into a rehabilitation pipe, it will be not avoided that mechanical properties become lower properties than high-pressure one without void. So, it is supposed that void remained into a rehabilitation pipe affects life-time of a rehabilitation pipe. Therefore the optimal molding condition for low contents of void and material selection are required.

CURING BEHAVIORE

Dielectrometer was used as the technique of measuring viscosity of a polymer material, and the

curing behavior and viscosity of resin were examined on real time by this technique. Generally the viscosity is decreased until the chemical reaction is started, then the viscosity is rapidly increased after the chemical reaction. The time until the chemical reaction is started can be regarded as curing time. The correlation between ion viscosity (the reciprocal value of the dielectric constant measured with dielectrometer) and viscosity obtained by rotation viscosimeter has already clarified. In this study, the dielectric constant of compound used in SMC was measured and an ion viscosity was calculated. Also viscosity of SMC was measured using Rheometer at each temperature. Then, in order to investigate the effects of change in the viscosity on the thickness of SMC, the thickness of SMC was measured at different temperature. Furthermore, the temperature of each SMC layer through thickness direction was investigated in a single-side curing state using a low-pressure molding system.

(1) Experimental method

1) Ion viscosity

Schematic drawing for measuring system of an ion viscosity is shown in Fig.1. First, TM sensor is beforehand heated to setting temperature, then a compound (3g) is set on a sensor after it reached setting temperature, and compressed with a glass board and weight.

Fig.1 Measurement system of an ion viscosity

2) Rheopexy viscosity of SMC

Schematic drawing for measuring system of rheopexy viscosity is shown in Fig.2. The measuring conditions are shown in Table 1.

Fig.2 Rheopexy viscosity

Table 1 measurement conditions of rheopexy viscosity

Item	Condition
Goods	plate/plate
Space	2mm
Sample	$\phi 40 \times 2\text{mm}$
Frequency	0.5Hz

3) Thickness of SMC using low-pressure molding system

The rubber sheet was put on the bottom disk of a compression machine (shown in photograph 1), and SMC sheet of 3mm was plied into 5ply. Pressure of 0.05MPa was applied to SMC by air pressure. Moreover, heating was taken only at a bottom side. A change in thickness was measured.

Photo-1 Press machine

4) Measurement of internal temperature

The internal temperature by single-sided curing using an examination equipment shown in Fig.3 was measured in each layers on SMC of 5plies.

Fig.3 Low-pressure molding system

(2) Results

The measurement result of ion viscosities is shown in Fig.4, and the result of rheopexy viscosity is shown in Fig.5. From these results of ion viscosity, when curing temperature was raised, the viscosity of compound was fallen, but curing time became short. The rheopexy viscosity of SMC including glass fiber shows the same tendency with ion viscosity not including glass fiber.

The change in thickness at each temperature is shown in Fig.6. Thickness was decreased with increase in molding time at all temperature. The thickness was changed until SMC was cured in the range from 70 to 90°C though it was low-pressure molding.

The internal temperature at 70°C is shown in Fig.7. Starting time of curing (namely kick-off) becomes long gradually as a distance from a heat source becomes far. The maximum exothermic temperature (namely the exothermic peak temperature) of each layer becomes high as the distance from a heat source becomes far, and the position of 10.6mm from a heat source was the highest exothermic temperature. The temperature was 121.4 °C. An outside temperature from its position was low, and it showed 115.1°C in the outermost layer.

Fig.4 Ion viscosities

Fig.5 Rheopexy viscosity

Fig.6 Thickness change examination

Fig.7 Internal temperature in SMC at 70°C

(3) Discussions

Ion viscosity of only compound and rheopexy viscosity of SMC were measured, and it was confirmed that the viscosity of resin was decreased at 60~80°C when resin was heated. Start time of kick-off becomes short when temperature becomes high. Molding has to be finished during the viscosity was low, so possible time of molding corresponds the above temperature region. From the experimental results of thickness change, SMC flowed in 70~90°C although in case of low-pressure molding. From the measurement result of internal temperature, the temperature of mold was transmitted to SMC, next SMC of the 1st layer generates heat by curing reaction, then the self-heat generation was transmitted to SMC of 2nd layer, finally a heat reaches the outermost layer. The exothermic peak temperature is located at 10.6mm from a heat source, so the temperature distribution did not symmetric through the thickness. From these result, the possibility of a low-pressure molding required for pipe rehabilitation method using SMC was indicated.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Plate was molded with SMC using a low pressure molding system shown in Fig.3. Thickness, gravity,

bending properties and generation of void were measured. As a comparison, plate which was molded by high pressure molding using same SMC was examined.

(1) Molding

SMC sheet of 3mm was plied into 2ply and molded according one-way heating using low pressure system. Molding pressure was 0.05MPa. Curing temperature of 60°C, 70°C, 80°C and 100°C was selected. In order to compare, SMC was molded by high pressure and high temperature.

(2) Experimental method

that the effects of low pressure and low temperature on the thickness of SMC, gravity, the void generating, and bending properties were investigated.

Thickness measurement was performed on specimen extracted from the central position of SMC. The thickness of the piece was measured with slide calipers. The 3-point bending test followed JIS K 7055 (Testing method for flexural properties of glass fiber reinforced plastics). Gravity of SMC was measured by the Archimedes method using the sample after a three point bending test. The amount of void was measured by image processing for the section of a sample

(3) Results and consideration

1) Thickness

The thickness of SMC is shown in Fig8. It was shown that the thickness of SMC in 80°C was thicker about 1mm than thickness of SMC at 60 to 70°C.

Fig.8 The thickness of SMC

2) Mechanical properties and gravity

Result of three point bending test and gravity measurement are shown in Fig.9. SMC at 60~70°C exhibited the same gravity and mechanical properties as SMC of high-pressure molding. Moreover, when the molding temperature was increased at 80~100°C, the mechanical properties became about 80~85% of h SMC with high pressure molding, and the gravity became extremely low.

Fig.9 Mechanical properties and gravity

3) Cross-sectional observation

SMC was observed on each molding conditions. Photograph of a cross-sectional observation is shown in photograph 2(a)-(f) . SMC was heated from the bottom side in these photographs. SMC with high pressure and high temperature molding as shown in picture-2(a) had few minute voids in the section. SMC which was molded in low-pressure at same temperature of the 140 °C is shown in Photograph-2(b). There were a lot of voids all over SMC, and the maximum size of void was 1mm. Molding time was very short because of high molding temperature and therefore SMC was cured before contained air in SMC and Styrene gas which occurs in molding escaped. Therefore big voids have remained in SMC . The cross-sectional photograph of SMC at 100 °C is shown in Photograph-2(c). In this molding condition, molding temperature is high, so viscosity of resin becomes low, then fluidity become high. Therefore the voids tends to gather at the upper side (opposite side of heating), however, SMC was still cured before void escaped because of short molding time. Therefore many voids was remained at the cross-section. The cross-sectional photograph of SMC at 80°C is shown in Photograph-2(d). It is shown that voids were gathered for the upper side at 80°C as well as the case that molding temperature was 100°C. However, the size of void was smaller compared with 100°C. The cross-sectional photographs of SMC at 70°C and 60°C are shown in Photograph-2(e)(f). In these case, big void was not observed, but there was small voids in the section. Void ratio of SMC was measured; void ratio was calculated by cross-sectional area of void by the cross-sectional area of the whole section.

Moreover, the section was divided into the upper side and the lower side (heat source side), and each void ratio was calculated as shown in Fig.10.

Fig.10 should show that the upper side has a higher void ratio than lower side. It was considered that void was moved to the upper side from the lower side at the time of heating. Moreover, it was showed that void was effectively decreased by curing at 70°C.

Photo2-(a) SMC (high pressure and high temperature molding)

Photo-2(b) SMC(0.05MPa × 140°C)

Photo-2(c) SMC(0.05MPa × 100°C)

Photo-2(d) SMC(0.05MPa × 80°C)

Photo-2(e) SMC(0.05MPa × 70°C)

Photo-2(f) SMC(0.05MPa × 60°C)

Fig.10 Void ratio

4) Discussions

SMC was molded by low pressure molding, and the thickness, viscosity and mechanical property were measured and cross-sectional observation was performed. In case of low temperature molding, SMC was compressed to the thickness direction, and void escaped from heat source to opposite side to it, therefore void was reduced. Consequently, mechanical property achieved the equivalent value with SMC by high pressure molding and it is considered that ideal molding was possible with low pressure and a single-side curing

CONCLUSION

An experiment about each of molding and a plate has been conducted about molding conditions and mechanical properties of SMC for sewer pipe maintenance by low pressure molding. In this study, conclusion can be made.

- In this case of 100% charge for SMC, if molding was performed at 60°C and 70°C, an air including SMC and a gas which generate during a molding were gathered for one side, and SMC was obtained high gravity and high mechanical property.